

EFFECTS OF DIFFERENT FACTORS OF STRUCTURES ON NATURAL TIME PERIOD

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Abstract

Indian standard suggests that the natural time period is dependent on a building and its base dimensions. In this study, the analysis is performed to determine variations in the natural period based on different building parameters. A total of 10 buildings are analyzed in detail. One of these buildings, specifically a five-storey structure, is selected as the reference and will be referred to as the Benchmark Building. It consists of a bare frame with a plinth beam (without a slab) at the ground floor level. Different types of buildings are assessed for various effects due to stiffness, mass, building height, and column orientation to investigate the natural period. The analysis is performed in a manner consistent with the work of C. V. R. Murty, augmented by the addition of an ETABS-based shell and membrane model. According to the test results from the conducted study, it is evident that as the stiffness, mass, and number of storeys of a building increase, the natural period also increases. Additionally, regarding column orientation, the natural period is longer in the shorter direction of column size compared to the longer direction. The comparative analysis indicates that the natural period is greater when assessed using ETABS. Furthermore, the natural period values from the ETABS-based membrane model are higher than those from the shell-based model.

Keywords: Building; Natural Time Period; Membrane; Shell.

1. INTRODUCTION

The design of buildings exposed to natural threats like earthquakes and typhoons requires the safety of structures, which is influenced by the natural frequencies and the extent of damping in each vibration mode. The dynamic characteristics of structures are determined by the primary natural frequency and the intensity of damping shown by each vibration mode. The fundamental frequency of a building and its damping significantly influence the level of its response. The fundamental natural period of vibration T_n of the building is a crucial factor for assessing seismic base shear. It relies on fundamental factors such as building height or the number of stories. Building periods predicted by these formulas are commonly utilized in practice, although it has been noted that there is room for further enhancement in these equations since height alone is not sufficient to account for period variation. It is also recognized that the period of a RC frame structure varies based on whether the longitudinal or transverse direction of the structure is taken into account.

The purpose of this study is to examine the impacts of building due to natural period which occurs during an earthquake in both directions, namely X and Y. The different effects related to natural period on various building types are illustrated in this study. For this, we conducted a case study based on the book “Earthquake Behavior of Buildings” by C. V. R. Murty. We assessed

the natural period for various building types in relation to different effects. We utilized the same model as outlined in C. V. R. Murty’s book and concurrently verified the natural period values for various effects using both the book and ETABS software. In ETABS, we performed an analysis of the natural period for various types of buildings, taking into account shell and membrane considerations. In the provided paper, comparative findings from C. V. R. Murty's book, the ETABS shell-based model, and the ETABS membrane-based model for natural period have been discussed.

2. DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF BUILDING

Buildings sway during seismic activity. This swaying results in inertia forces being created within the structure. Both the severity and length of the swaying, along with the extent of the inertia forces generated in a building, are influenced by the building's features, known as their dynamic characteristics, as well as the properties of the seismic shaking itself. The key dynamic characteristics of buildings include oscillation modes and damping. An oscillation mode of a building is characterized by its corresponding Natural Period and Deformed Shape in which it moves. In the present paper, the examination of the natural period of a building is considered.

Natural Period

Natural Period T_n of a building is the time taken by it to undergo one complete cycle of oscillation. It is an inherent property of a building controlled by its mass m and stiffness k . These three quantities are related by its units are seconds (s). $T_n = 2\pi\sqrt{(m/k)}$

The reciprocal ($1/T_n$) of natural period of a building is called the Natural Frequency f_n ; its unit is Hertz (Hz). Buildings that are heavy (with larger mass m) and flexible (with smaller stiffness k) have larger natural period than light and stiff buildings. Buildings oscillate by translating along X, Y or Z directions, or by rotating about X, Y or Z axes, or by a combination of all. When a building oscillates, there is an associated shape of oscillation.

The building offers least resistance when shaken at its natural frequency (or natural period). Hence, it undergoes larger oscillation when shaken at its natural frequency than at other frequencies.

Usually, natural periods (T_n) of 1 to 20 storey normal reinforced concrete and steel buildings are in the range of 0.05 - 2.00s. In building design practice, engineers usually work with T_n and not f_n . Resonance will occur in a building, only if frequency at which ground shakes is steady at or near any of the natural frequencies of building and applied over an extended period of time.

Factors Influencing Natural Period

Numerical findings are utilized to clarify the idea of natural period and the elements that affect it. Reinforced concrete moment resistant frame structures are employed to demonstrate this concept; several characteristics of these structures are outlined in Table 1. A total of 10 buildings have been considered. One of these structures, specifically a five-storey building, is selected as the reference point and will be referred to as the Benchmark Building from this point onward. It is a basic frame with a plinth beam (without a slab) on the ground floor level. The specifications of this benchmark structure are presented in Figure 1.

3. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Structural Element Sizes:

Beams: $300 \times 400mm$

Columns: $400 \times 400mm$ Slab $150mm$ thick Material Properties:

Grade of Concrete: M30

Grade of Steel Reinforcement Bars: Fe 415 Loading:

Dead Load on beams from infill wall: $10 kN/m$ Openings in walls: 20%

Live load on floor: $3 kN/m^2$

Figure 1 Five storey Benchmark Building Elevation & plan of 5-storey benchmark building with moment frame grid (in mm).

Table 1 Buildings considered to illustrate concept of natural period

Building	Description	No. of Storeys	Number of Bays		Column Dimension (mm x mm)
			XDir.	YDir.	
A	2 Storey Building	2	4	3	400 x 400
B	Benchmark 5 Storey Building	5	4	3	400 x 400
C	Benchmark Building with Rectangular Columns oriented along X- direction	5	4	3	550 x 300
D	Benchmark Building with Rectangular Columns oriented along Y- direction	5	4	3	300 x 550
E	10 Storey Building with varying Column Size along Building Height	10	4	3	Upper 5 Storeys: (400 x 400)
					Bottom 5 Storeys: (600 x 600)
F	10 Storey Building	10	4	3	600 x 600
G	25 Storey Building with varying Column Size along Building Height	25	4	3	Upper 5 Storeys: (400 x 400)
					Middle 10 Storeys: (600 x 600)
					Bottom 10 Storeys: (800 x 800)
H	25 Storey Building	25	4	3	800 x 800
J	25 Storey Building with imposed mass 10% larger than Building H	25	4	3	800 x 800
K	25 Storey Building with imposed mass 20% larger than Building H	25	4	3	800 x 800

Note

- Bay length in each plan direction is 4m (Centre to Centre).
- All columns at each storey are of the same size.
- All beams in all buildings are of the same size (300 mm x 400 mm).

As per this above table, these are the 10 types of buildings as per C.V.R. Murty's book. According to this classification of buildings the various effects due to natural period are as follows:

Effect of Stiffness

To check this effect of stiffness building types E, F, G and H have considered from above 10 types of buildings. Increasing the column size increases both stiffness and mass of buildings. But, when the percentage increase in stiffness as a result of increase in column size is larger than the percentage increase in mass, the natural period reduces. Hence, the increase in column size reduces the natural period of buildings.

Buildings E and F are two 10-storey buildings. From which building E is with different column sizes along the elevation and building F has column size of 600x600 throughout the height, while building E has smaller column size of 400x400 in the upper 5 storeys. Thus, building F with 600x600 column throughout is relatively stiffer than Building E and the fundamental period of the stiffer building F is only marginally smaller than that of the building E.

The most of the deformation is occurring only in the lower storeys because of shear-type of lateral deformation in the building, where the columns size is same. Hence, the influence on the overall natural period is not perceptible. But, if column sizes are changed in the lower storeys also, the natural period will differ significantly. Between buildings G and H, building H is much stiffer. But, while increasing stiffness, the mass is also increased.

Following Figure 2 and Figure 3 shows comparative results of natural period as per book and as per ETABS shell based and membrane-based model in X and Y directions respectively. From both the figures it states that, as the building F is stiffer than building E and building H is also stiffer than building G natural period increases as the stiffness of building increases. Comparative analysis results shows that the natural period is more when it analyses by using ETABS. And from ETABS based model, values of natural period for membrane-based model are more than shell-based model

Figure 2 Effect of Stiffness on Natural Period in coordinate X – Direction

Figure 3 Effect of Stiffness on Natural Period in coordinate Y – Direction

Effect of Mass

To check this effect of mass building types H, J and K have considered from above 10 types of buildings. Mass of a building that is effective in lateral oscillation during earthquake shaking is called the seismic mass of the building. It is the sum of its seismic masses at different floor levels. Seismic mass at each floor level is equal to full dead load plus appropriate fraction of live load. The fraction of live load depends on the intensity of the live load and how it is connected to the floor slab. An increase in mass of a building increases its natural period. Buildings H, J and K are all 25- storey buildings with same plan size, elevation and column sizes, but with different floor mass. Imposed floor mass in building H is 2,150kN, while that in buildings J and K are 10% and 20% larger, respectively. Fundamental translational natural periods of heavier buildings K and J are larger than that of building H. Figure 4 and Figure 5 shows comparative results of natural period as per book and as per ETABS shell based and membrane-based model in X and Y directions respectively. From both the figures it states that, building K is heavier than building H and J. As the mass of building increases natural period of building increases. Comparative analysis results shows that the natural period is more when it analyses by using ETABS. And from ETABS based model, values of natural period for membrane-based model are more than shell-based model

Figure 4 Effect of Mass on Natural Period in coordinate X – Direction

Figure 5 Effect of Mass on Natural Period in coordinate Y – Direction

Effect of Building Height

To check this effect building types A, B, F and H have considered. As the height of building increases, its mass increases but its overall stiffness decreases. Hence, the natural period of a building increases with increase in height. Buildings A, B, F and H have same plan size, but are of different heights. Taller buildings have larger fundamental natural period than shorter ones, the fundamental translational natural periods for base model of 25-storey building H, 10- storey building F, 5-storey building B and 2-storey building are 3.14s, 1.35s, 0.89s and 0.45s, respectively.

Comparative results of natural period for this effect as per book and as per ETABS shell based and membrane-based model in X and Y directions are shown in Figure 6 and

Figure 7 respectively. From both the figures it shows that, building H is tallest one as compares to other buildings. As the height of building increases natural period of building increases. For building type A, B, and F there is slight difference of natural period but for building type H there is a vast difference in natural period values. Comparative analysis results shows that the natural period is more when it analyses by using ETABS. And from ETABS based model, values of natural period for membrane-based model are more than shell-based model.

Figure 6 Effect of Building Height on Natural Period in coordinate X – Direction

Figure 7 Effect of Building Height on Natural Period in coordinate Y-Direction

Effect of Column Orientation

To check this effect building types B, C and D have considered. Orientation of rectangular columns influences lateral stiffness of buildings along two horizontal directions. Hence, changing the orientation of columns changes the translational natural period of buildings. Building type B is 5 storey building having square columns of size 400 mm x 400 mm size. Buildings C and D are two 5-storey buildings with same column area, but with different orientation of rectangular columns. Longer side of 550mmx300mm columns is oriented along X-direction in building C, and along Y-direction in building D. Lateral stiffness of columns along longer direction is more. Hence, natural period of buildings along the longer direction of column cross-section is smaller than that along the shorter direction.

The results for this effect are shown in Figure 8 and in Figure 9 as per book and as per ETABS shell based and membrane-based model in X and Y directions respectively. From Figure 8 it shows that, natural period is more for type D building than B and C. But from Figure 9 it states that, natural period of type C is more than type B as well as type D. For this effect the results of natural period are not relevant. Comparative analysis results shows that the natural period is more when it analyses by using ETABS. And from ETABS based model, values of natural period for membrane-based model are more than shell-based model.

Figure 8 Effect of Column Orientation on Natural Period in coordinate X – Direction

Figure 9 Effect of Column Orientation on Natural Period in coordinate Y – Direction

4. CONCLUSION

All the test results of this case study which are taken from the book “Earthquake Behaviour of Buildings” of C.V.R. Murty are get verified. As per the various effects, natural period of a building increases when the stiffness of building increases with the increasing mass of building, natural period also increases as the height of building increases, natural period increases.

As per the column orientation of a building, natural period of buildings along the longer direction of column cross-section is smaller than that along the shorter direction. we have plotted two consecutive graphs for each effect showing variation in natural period as per the various types of buildings, in X and Y Direction. So natural period is more in all graphs of Y direction as compare to graphs in X direction.

As we have considered here ETABS based model for shell and membrane type and the results of them are compared with the base model it is shown that, for every effect of natural period, values of natural period for base model are lesser than ETABS based membrane and shell model and the values of membrane-based model are more than shell-based model.

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